

TREATIES OF PARIS: FROM EUROPEAN (POLITICAL) ORDER TO EUROPEAN LEGAL ORDER

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Abstract. *The paper seeks to individualize the place and the role of the treaties of Paris for peace making in Europe, contributing to a European political order and ultimately creating a European legal order. No doubt Paris constitutes emblematically the epicenter of various treaties concluded for both political and legal reasons. Throughout the history, the treaties of Paris put an end to disputes or prescribed rules for further association, creating rights and responsibilities for the signing parties. After the World War I the treaties of Paris came with innovations in legal matters that influenced the European political order for a long time. It was a gradual accumulation of knowledge and expertise in establishing and keeping peace all over Europe, beginning with the treaty of 1214 and ending with the treaty of 1920. Fragile peace was restored, but for how long. After the World War II the treaties of Paris started to have a double value. On the one hand, they have continued to play an important role in peace-building. And what is more important, on the other hand, the Treaty of Paris of 1951 put the brick to the European integration process and creation of the European legal order. The European legal order is the creation of European states that established the European Coal and Steel Community, found the European Atomic Energy Community, developed the European Economic Community and formed the European Union. The European legal order of the European Union (inherent part of European integration) has the qualities of the most advanced and versatile form of European order. The European legal order of the European Union emerged in the result of past experiences, learnt lessons and shaped will to be an example and multiplier of peace not only in Europe, but all over the world. Moreover, the world follows Europeanization of national legal orders and Europeanization of the international legal order that speaks about the European Union as a global actor.*

Keywords: *Treaties of Paris, European Union, European political order, European legal order, international legal order.*

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INTRODUCTION

The concluded treaties throughout the time bearing the name Paris constitute a unique experience in Europe in terms of establishing peace, alliances, establishing the European political order and the European legal order. The typology of concluded treaties is quite diverse from a historical point of view covering a large period of time beginning with 1214 up to nowadays. The treaties started to regulate minor local disputes ascending to regulate major European priorities and, finally, matters on global level.

The paper seeks to analyze and evaluate the contribution of the treaties of Paris in regulating minor local disputes to major objectives at European and global levels. Considering the treaties of Paris are associated with peace-making, peace-keeping and peace-building, they shaped unequivocally the European political order and the European legal order. On its turn, the *acquis communautaire* has exerted a great influence on national legal orders of all Member States and on the international legal order, in this case, speaking about the Europeanization process at national, supranational and global layers.

The treaties of Paris contributed to and determined inextricably the economic and legal integration of Europe that is the European Union. Moreover, even if the European Union has no explicit political treaty concluded by the Member States, the undeniable global actorness of the European Union on international arena discloses it is implied without being stated political power. To come to such an end it is fair to look retrospectively to the agreements that make the corpus of the treaties of Paris. The legacy of the treaties of Paris has both a regional / European and international added value.

1. PARIS: A FORGERY OF TREATIES

A commencing question is why Paris is the place and the name of many treaties in Europe and worldwide. There are a couple of reasons to take into consideration. France has been an important player, sometimes a major power, in the previous millennium. It is obvious France used to be a mediator in various regional and international negotiations with different parts. The cultural aura of France and Paris also played an important role in considering it a place for reconciliation. The last, but probably the most, French was the language of diplomacy for a very long time, only recently being replaced by English. This meant that French was the working language in international relations and international treaties.

So, Paris has been an attractive pole in settling regional and international differenda due to the above-mentioned reasons, i.e. power, culture and language.

2. TREATIES OF PARIS: SYNOPSIS

The first treaties of Paris go back to the beginning of the second millennium. There are a lot of treaties regulating different disputes; scholars count a number of sixty-seven. And there are two treaties that refer strictly to the European Communities. Chronologically they stretch from 1214 to 1952.

In the 13th century there were signed 4 treaties (1214, 1229, 1259, 1295). In all treaties on settling disputes and alliances, France was the dominant party.

In the 14th century there were signed 6 treaties (1303, 1310, 1320, 1323, 1327, 1355). By this century it became a tradition to sign treaties in Paris. The innovation was introduced by the treaty of 1323, which did not include France as a party of the document.

In the 15th century it was signed 1 treaty (1498).

In the 16th century there were signed 2 treaties (1515, 1600).

In the 17th century there were signed 6 treaties (1623, 1626, 1634, 1635, 1657, 1662).

In the 18th century there were signed 14 treaties (1718, 1749, 1761, 1763, 1783a, 1783b, 1783c, 1783d, 1784, 1786, 1796a, 1796b, 1796c, 1796d).

In the 19th century there were signed 22 treaties (1801a, 1801b, 1802a, 1802b, 1802c, 1806a, 1806b, 1810a, 1810b, 1810c, 1810d, 1810e, 1814, 1815, 1816, 1817, 1856, 1857a, 1857b, 1879a, 1879b, 1898).

In the 20th century there were signed 11 treaties (1900, 1918, 1920, 1928, 1947a, 1947b, 1947c, 1947d, 1947e, 1951, 1952).

ACCORDS

Alongside with the treaties of Paris, there is an array of peace accords that were also signed in Paris. Among them there could be mentioned the accord of 1973 ending the war in Vietnam and the accord of 1991 marking the end of the Vietnamese-Cambodian war.

CONVENTIONS

In the past three centuries there have been signed 13 conventions in Paris on various issues (1858, 1865, 1875, 1883, 1902, 1904, 1919, 1920, 1928, 1950, 1960, 1992, 2005).

PROTOCOLS

In the 20th centuries there were signed five protocols in Paris (1941a, 1941b, 1941c, 1941d, 1954).

CHARTER

Among the acts of Paris, there is one charter for a new Europe (1990).

DECLARATION

Such an act was signed in 2005 on efficient aid.

AGREEMENTS

There are two Paris agreements (1946, 2015) concerning different issues.

PARIS ACTS

Ever since pre-classical antiquity, peace treaties have been important instruments for ending wars as well as for the political and legal organization of international communities. Peace treaties were of particular importance to Europe and the West. The relative number of wars which were ended through peace treaties steadily rose from less than half in the 16th century to almost 90 per cent at the beginning of the 20th century. Peace treaties played a primary role in the formation of Europe's classical law of nations.¹

To sum up, needless to say that Paris has become an important place of power in hosting throughout the history signing multiple acts such as treaties, accords, protocols, conventions, charters, declarations or agreements. Thus, Paris has played a special role in regional and international disputes on restoring peace and respecting human rights of various nationals. These are two basic and uniting elements of the above-mentioned Paris acts. They also used to influence the history of Europe and worldwide, political order of Europe and legal order of the nations and of the international law.

3. TREATIES ESTABLISHING THE EUROPEAN (POLITICAL) ORDER

In large the majority of Paris acts are peace treaties that contributed to a more or less stable order all over Europe, on the one hand. On the other hand, it seems that the Paris treaties dating back to about one century ago cemented what we call nowadays European political order. For that to happen, a necessary condition is to

¹ Randall Lesaffer, "Actors: Peace Treaties and the Formation of International Law", in *The Oxford Handbook of the History of International Law*, ed. Bardo Fassbender and Anne Peters (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012), 71–94.

convene on certain rules of conduct between and among the implied actors. Organized political institutions would keep the peace and uniform laws that applied to all parties are conducive to stability. But stability is always challenged by social, political, economic, etc. development. By using the comparative political history, the American political scientist Francis Fukuyama theorizes in a series of books on the development of political order beginning from pre-human times and ending the analysis to present days; he advances three components that are worth mentioning for the stability of a political system: strong and modern; rule of law; and accountable.²

The scientist Johan Olsen speaks about democratic accountability and a Europe struggling to find viable answers to the questions of who and what shall constitute Europe and how to develop legitimate political institutions for governing it. This is about political order and change, rules for living together, the role of democratic politics in society and the relations between political organization and civilized coexistence, and the study of the political. Modern democracies live with unresolved conflicts, and accountability regimes are part of an institutional arrangement for preserving order and continuity and also for creating dynamics and change. Accountability processes take place within settled and unsettled orders, and they affect and are affected by existing orders. Without denying the importance of contending interests, power struggles, strategic behaviour, non-cooperative games, and (re)distributional battles, attention is directed towards the search for unity, political cohesion and solidarity based upon the informed voluntary consent of the people through reflection and reasoned deliberation among individuals with different values, interests, understandings and resources.³

The politics of identity has had enormous salience in the new Europe and for the European Union at this juncture of its development, because the European Union is moving from issues of instrumental problem-solving to fundamental questions about its nature as a part-formed polity.⁴

4. TREATIES ESTABLISHING THE EUROPEAN LEGAL ORDER

As the connector to the acts on European legal order is Paris, consequently it is fair to mention two important treaties that contributed to the formation of the European legal order by establishing the European communities and later the European Union. There are two major treaties that were signed in Paris: the *Treaty*

² Cf. Francis Fukuyama, *Origins of Political Order: From Prehuman times to the French Revolution* (New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2011); Francis Fukuyama, *Political Order and Political Decay: From the Industrial Revolution to the Present Day* (New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2014).

³ Johan Olsen, "Democratic Accountability and the Changing European Political Order", *European Law Journal* 24, no. 1 (January 2018): 77–94.

⁴ Brigid Laffan, "The Politics of Identity and Political Order in Europe", *Journal of Common Market Studies* 34, no. 1 (March 1996): 81–102.

establishing the European Coal and Steel Community (18 April 1951) and the Treaty establishing the European Defence Community (27 May 1952). Even if the second of these treaties was not ratified, however it participated in the process of law-making at pan-European level and could be revived in an alternative format in defending the values of the European Union in reclaiming times.

The first treaty of the European communities, as it is known as the Treaty establishing the European Coal and Steel Community, makes part of the founding treaties in the process of European integration. It is the milestone of the whole process of European integration and of the process forming the European legal order both for the European communities and later the European Union.

Since the founding of the European Coal and Steel Community, the European Union has developed a self-contained legal system in which EU law will be interpreted consistently across all Member States. According to the Court of Justice conclusions, the European Union represents a new legal order of international law. The legal order created by the European community has become a permanent feature of political reality in the Member States of the European Union. The uniformity in application of European law is ensured by national courts. So, this speaks in favour of a veritable legal order at the level of the European Union, which is put in practice both by supranational courts of the European Union and national courts of the Member States.

Klaus-Dieter Borchardt – a European Union official since 1987, Deputy Head of Cabinet and then Head of Cabinet for the Commissioner for Agriculture from 2004 to 2010, an Honorary Professor at the University of Würzburg, where he has taught European law since 2001 – underlines that “The legal order created by the European Union (EU) has already become an established component of our political life and society. Each year, on the basis of the Union Treaties, thousands of decisions are taken that crucially affect the EU Member States and the lives of their citizens. Individuals have long since ceased to be merely citizens of their country, town or district; they are also Union citizens. For this reason alone, it is of crucial importance that they should be informed about the legal order that affects their daily lives. Yet the complexities of the Union’s structure and its legal order are not easy to grasp. This is partly due to the wording of the Treaties themselves, which is often somewhat obscure, with implications which are not easy to appreciate. An additional factor is the unfamiliarity of many concepts with which the Treaties seek to master the situation. The following pages are an attempt to clarify the structure of the Union and the supporting pillars of the European legal order, and thus help to lessen any lack of understanding among the citizens of the EU.”⁵

To a final question what overall picture emerges of the EU’s legal order, Klaus-Dieter Borchardt states that “The EU’s legal order is the true foundation of the Union, giving it a common system of law under which to operate. Only by

⁵ Klaus-Dieter Borchardt, *The ABC of European Union Law* (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2010), 7.

creating new law and upholding it can the Union’s underlying objectives be achieved. The EU legal order has already accomplished a great deal in this respect. It is thanks not least to this new legal order that the largely open borders, the substantial trade in goods and services, the migration of workers and the large number of transnational links between companies have already made the common market part of everyday life for some 500 million people. Another, historically important, feature of the Union legal order is its peace making role. With its objective of maintaining peace and liberty, it replaces force as a means of settling conflicts by rules of law that bind both individuals and the Member States into a single Community. As a result the Union legal order is an important instrument for the preservation and creation of peace. The community of law of the EU and its underlying legal order can survive only if compliance with and safeguarding of that legal order are guaranteed by the two cornerstones: the direct applicability of Union law and the primacy of Union law over national law. These two principles, the existence and maintenance of which are resolutely upheld by the Court of Justice, guarantee the uniform and priority application of Union law in all Member States. For all its imperfections, the EU legal order makes an invaluable contribution towards solving the political, economic and social problems of the Member States of the Union.”⁶ The European Union is a creator of law and a community based on law.

5. THE EUROPEANIZATION PROCESS

The Europeanization process has intrinsic ties with the effects of the treaties of Paris. The treaties of Paris have played a preparing role for future negotiations of a united Europe and contributed evolutionarily to the emergence of the Europeanization process both at theoretical and practical levels.

The consequences of European integration process and the consolidation of democratic values are indissolubly linked to the concept of Europeanization, because European integration is perceived as a process through which the national policies of the Member States change and engage in supranational policies of the European Union through the transfer of competences and, at the same time, by blurring the limits of competences. Empirical studies on Europeanization reveal two conceptual definitions:

- *in stricto sensu*, all processes attached to the European Union are represented by the varying nature of the relations between the Union and the Member States;
- *in lato sensu*, the concept, in a broad sense, separate from the European Union, in studying Europe.

Starting from these two distinct definitions, the conceptions of the term Europeanization would focus on specific characteristics, which are rigorously

⁶ Borchardt, 125.

synthesized by Ian Bache and George Stephen.⁷ For example, five possible acceptations of the term 'Europeanization' are distinguished:

- changes within the external territorial borders;
- creation of governance institutions at European level;
- direct incursion into national and sub-national governance systems;
- exporting typical and distinct political and organizational patterns for Europe outside European territory;
- political project aimed at a more united and politically strong Europe.

At the same time there are identified five different contexts in which the term "Europeanisation" was used by scientific researchers:

- to refer to the creation of governance institutions at European level;
- to refer to examples where distinct European organizational and management models have been exported outside Europe's territorial borders;
- to denote the achievement of Europe's political unification;
- as a process by which domestic policy is an increasingly subject to the policy-making process in Europe.

It is also stated that Europeanization is the most often used term in one of five ways:

- a process of top-down internal change under the influence of the European Union;
- creating new competences for the European Union;
- creating a new European model of internal policy;
- a horizontal transfer or 'cross-loading' of concepts and policies between states;
- an increased interaction in both ways between the states and the European Union.

Out of these acceptations, we observe two important aspects: those that are specific to the European Union and those that are non-specific for the European Union.

The evaluation of the concept of Europeanization is possibly based on the categories of interests, institutions and ideas in order to clarify the dynamics of the European integration process through the acceptance and assimilation of the *acquis communautaire* for compliance with normative legal norms. Interests are causal as they directly determine policy positions by establishing a distribution of societal references taken into account by national officials as they seek to create electoral coalitions capable of gaining and maintaining power policies. Institutions influence actors' actions and inactivity by assigning power to actors, but not to others, structuring the content and succession of policy-making, and giving the state opportunities and constraints on it, as state officials seek social support for their choices of policies. Ideas matter because they allow actors to manage the

uncertainty about the alleged consequences of alternative choices and because they endow actors with a symbolic and conceptual language to promote their causes. In the context of strategic interaction among many actors, common ideas can drive convergence of expectations and strategies, facilitating collective agreement and outcomes.

Europeanization undergoes multiple layers, the most significant residing in politics and law, and influencing directly whole societies and long-running processes both in Europe and worldwide. The rule of law and protection of human rights are deeply incremented by the process of Europeanization both at the level of Member States and third parties.

6. THE EUROPEANIZATION OF NATIONAL LEGAL ORDERS

The Europeanization of national legal orders occurs differently for beneficiary countries. One aspect is related to EU Member States and the other to partner countries according to international (bilateral / multilateral) agreements concluded with third countries.

The *acquis communautaire* is the law of the European Union as a supranational organization. It regulates intra-community relations, on the one hand. On the other hand, it is directly applied by national law of the Member States. By absorption, it becomes an integral part of national legislation of the Member States. European law prevails over national law of the Member States.

Partner countries of the European Union also face influences of the European Union law in their national legislations. The process is called harmonization or approximation. The goal resides in upgrading national law of partner countries in accordance to the standards of the European law. Special attention is paid to the rule of law concerning human rights and institutional functioning. But for sure, it is not limited to them.

7. THE EUROPEANIZATION OF INTERNATIONAL LEGAL ORDER

The Europeanization process is also about values, but which values. European values are in fact general human values. What the European Union did is that it did not treat these values as ethical ones, but incorporated them in the European law. The difference moves from moral responsibility to legal responsibility.

The values that are protected by the European Union law have made an object of direct transfer to international law that regulates the global society. This has not claimed extra discussions due to the nature of the values that are general

⁷ Ian Bache and Stephen George, *Politics in the European Union* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2006).

human *per se*. For the time being the general tendency is characterized by the Europeanization process of international legal order.

8. THE LEGACY OF THE TREATIES OF PARIS

From the scientific point of view, all treaties of Paris bear a special value. Out of all, the concluded treaties after the WW I are the most important for Europe and humanity in terms of political order and human rights. Alan Sharp argues for a reassessment of the Paris conferences. He focuses on the vast and unprecedented disruption and dislocation caused by the collapse of four empires at the end of the WW I. Peace was the best solution. He also refers to the provisions and deliberations of the Paris conferences, which are of major importance to the wider history of the 20th century: national self-determination, collective security, international law, and human rights. In essence, these were the last of the great power conferences after Vienna (1814–15) and Berlin (1884), being an essential starting point for the century that followed. In his book, Alan Sharp reassesses the Paris conferences and places them excellently within a much wider context than they normally inhabit: one reaching right up to the present day.⁸

In other words, the treaties of Paris encompass a large array of issues from the very beginning of such conferences till the last ones that regulate human relations in various legal disputes. Among them could be mentioned peace-building, peace-keeping, recognition of the right to self-determination, recognition of new states / nations, security, development of international law and human rights law.

For instance, Edward J. Jr. Renehan, author of *The Treaty of Paris: The Precursor to a New Nation* offers an engaging, curriculum-based look at the people and events behind this extraordinary achievement. Excerpts from primary documents, lively biographical details, and first-person narratives highlight the Treaty's impact on American history. In Paris during the spring, summer, and autumn of 1782, four remarkable Americans represented the United States in negotiations that brought an end to the American Revolutionary War. John Adams, Benjamin Franklin, John Jay and Henry Laurens worked to bring about British recognition of American independence and a cessation to hostilities. At times at loggerheads with the British and at times at loggerheads with each other, these three great patriots nevertheless won a tremendous diplomatic victory for their country in securing the peace.⁹

The preliminary articles were signed in 1782 and the final treaty was signed in 1793. The American Continental Congress ratified the Treaty on January 14,

⁸ Alan Sharp, *Consequences of Peace: The Versailles Settlement, Aftermath and Legacy 1919–2010* (London: Haus, 2010).

⁹ Edward J. Jr. Renehan, *The Treaty of Paris: The Precursor to a new Nation* (New York: Chelsea House, 2007).

1784; France in March 1784 and Great Britain in April 1794. The articles of the treaty contained such provisions:

- Britain acknowledged the United States to be free, sovereign and independent states with the British Crown, heirs and successors relinquishing claim to government, property and territorial rights.
- Established geographical boundaries between the United States and British North America.
- Granted fishing rights to United States fishermen in the Grand Banks of the coast of Newfoundland and Gulf of St. Lawrence.
- Past debts to be paid by creditors on either side.
- Congress will recommend to states legislatures to recognize ownership of confiscated land and proved restitution.
- United States will prevent future confiscation of loyalist property.
- Prisoners of war are to be released.
- Britain and United States to be given perpetual access to the Mississippi River.
- Territories captured by America after the treaty will be returned without compensation.
- Ratification is to occur within 6 months from its signing.

Although the treaties of Paris once started to deal with peace-making, in the end the major concern shifted to secure the fragile peace as discussions and regulations on human rights witnessed a huge leap in the years to come.

CONCLUSION

The treaties of Paris became a spring of wisdom both by their number and by their quality that influenced diplomatically, politically and legally not only Europe, but the whole world. Even if the instruments of the treaties of Paris are of diplomatic nature, they contributed to shaping the political order, in the beginning, and the legal order of the European community recently.

The treaties of Paris contain in themselves experiences of living together in a diverse Europe. They put the brick to the development of acknowledged rules of political conduct among European actors and later international actors. They also put the brick to uniting Europe around convened values.

The treaties of Paris constantly pursued establishing and securing peace in Europe and worldwide. United Europe resulted from an insecure environment. The constitutional treaties of the European Community / European Union found an inspirational model in the historical treaties of Paris as they promoted positive and constructive concepts on human development.

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